

Physicochemical Properties of Hydroxamic Acids

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Physicochemical properties of *para*- and *meta*-chloro-substituted-hydroxamic acids are described. The molecular weights of hydroxamic acids are determined. The thermodynamic ionisation constants (pK_a) of the hydroxamic acids in 50% (v/v) dioxan-water media are determined at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The rate of alkaline hydrolysis of hydroxamic acids and reaction mechanism are discussed

RECENTLY many analogs have been prepared by the introduction of various substituent groups in different positions with the hope of developing reagents with superior analytical properties. Hydroxamic acids have been extensively employed in analytical and medicinal chemistry. Their physicochemical properties have been found to have a strong bearing on its effectiveness as an analytical or biological reagent. The reactions of *meta*- and *para*-chloro-substituted-furo- and -thenohydroxamic acids with several metal ions have been studied for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of the respective metal ions¹.

In the present investigation, physicochemical properties, viz. DTA, TG, non-aqueous titration, thermodynamic ionisation constant (pK_a) and alkaline hydrolysis of *meta*- and *para*-chloro-substituted-hydroxamic acids have been described.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade unless otherwise specified.

Hydroxamic acids were synthesised as described elsewhere². Double-distilled water was tested³ for the absence of carbonate. Dioxan and methanol were purified⁴ before use. Tetrabutyl ammonium hydroxide (0.1M) was prepared⁵ in dioxan-water medium. Potassium methoxide was prepared⁶ by reacting potassium metal with methanol and diluting it with benzene so that benzene-methanol ratio remains 10 : 1. Thymol blue (0.1%) was prepared in DMF or methanol. Sodium hydroxide (0.1M) was prepared in 60% dioxan-water and standardised⁷ with potassium hydrogen phthalate. Ferric chloride solution (0.2%, w/v) in 1.0M HCl was prepared⁸ and used for complexation.

A N.P.L.-certified apparatus of Gallenkamp, Technico grade A was used for measurements. A Systronics digital pH-meter equipped with glass and saturated calomel electrodes was used for pH measurements. The platinum and calomel (saturated

with KCl in methanol) electrodes were used for non-aqueous titrations. The pH-meter was calibrated in 0.01 unit of pH. A Cambridge potentiometer equipped with platinum and calomel (saturated with KCl in methanol) electrodes was used for potentiometric titrations.

The TG and DTA curves of hydroxamic acids in air were recorded on a Mettler thermal analyser maintaining the following parameters in all the experiments : TG range, 1 mg full scale sensitivity ; DTA range, 50 V ; heating rate $-8^\circ/\text{min}$, gas flow rate, 100 ml min^{-1} ; mass of the sample, 10 mg. Alumina was used as a reference material for DTA.

Spectrophotometer : Absorbance measurements were made on a Carl Zeiss Jena model VSU2-P spectrophotometer.

Non-aqueous titration : Dimethylformamide or ethanol (20 ml) was added to a known amount of hydroxamic acid and the solution was stirred with a magnetic stirrer under nitrogen atmosphere. Indicator solution (2-3 drops) was then added to it and titrated against 0.1 M potassium methoxide in nitrogen atmosphere.

Determination of ionisation constants : The titration procedure was essentially the same as recommended by Agrawal *et al.*⁸.

Alkaline hydrolysis : To a 0.01 M solution (25 ml) of hydroxamic acid in dioxan (thermostated at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$) was added 0.1 M solution (25 ml) of sodium hydroxide and thoroughly mixed. Aliquots of the reaction mixture were withdrawn periodically starting from the time of mixing and complexed with FeCl_3 solution (1 ml). The complex is then diluted to 10 ml with dioxan-water to get a final composition of the solvent 1 : 1 dioxan : water. The absorbance of the pink coloured ferric hydroxamate was measured at the respective maximum absorbance against the FeCl_3 blank. Absorbance at infinite time (A_∞) was measured by keeping the reaction mixture for 48 h.

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TABLE 1—THERMAL DATA OF HYDROXAMIC ACIDS

Sl. no.	Hydroxamic acid	M.p. °C	TG (wt. loss)		DTA (°C)		
			°C		Endo.	Exo	
			°C	°C		1st	2nd
1.	<i>N-p</i> -Chlorophenyl-2-furo-	164	165-330	340-600	165	210	350
2.	<i>N-p</i> -Chlorophenyl-2-theno-	143	150-550	560-650	145	150	570
3.	<i>N-p</i> -Chlorophenylpicolino-	120	135-300	315-400	120	210	310
4.	<i>N-p</i> -Chlorophenylquinaldino-	120	125-250	260-450	120	190	380
5.	<i>N-p</i> -Chlorophenylbenzo-	157	160-250	255-410	158	200	350
6.	<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenyl-2-furo-	165	170-260	260-450	168	220	380
7.	<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenyl-2-theno-	120	125-210	220-500	120	170	340
8.	<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenylpicolino-	117	118-175	180-560	118	151	530
9.	<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenylquinaldino-	126	125-250	250-480	125	220	400
10.	<i>N-m</i> -Chlorophenylbenzo-	117	117-180	190-510	118	200	480

The rate constant (*K*) for the first order reaction was calculated by equation (1)

$$K = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{A_0 - A_\infty}{A_t - A_\infty} \quad (1)$$

where *A*₀ and *A*_∞ are the absorbances of the reaction mixture at zero and at infinite time and *A*_t is the absorbance at time *t*.

Results and Discussion

TG and DTA : The thermal data of the chloro-substituted-hydroxamic acids are recorded in Table 1.

The hydroxamic acids were heated upto 700° in an atmosphere of air. The thermograms show no change in weight till the melting point of hydroxamic acids, indicating the compounds melted till it was finally converted to tars. The DTA curves show mainly one endothermic and two exothermic peaks. The endotherm corresponds to the melting of the compounds, and then decomposition starts as shown by the exothermic peak. The decomposition is gradual and the end is denoted by an exotherm showing the complete decomposition of the acids to tars. The products obtained by the thermal decomposition of the hydroxamic acids were analysed and found mainly to be their carboxylic acids, anilides and finally tars.

Non-aqueous titrations : The heterocyclic hydroxamic acids were titrated visually in dimethylformamide using thymol blue as indicator against 0.1 *M* sodium methoxide. The potentiometric titrations were also performed using platinum and calomel electrodes (saturated KCl in methanol) in presence of nitrogen. The results are shown in Table 2.

The indicator colour in dimethylformamide changed from yellow to red, corresponding the change from acid to base, for compounds sl. nos. 3, 4, 8 and 9 (Table 2), and from yellowish to orange-red and pink orange for compounds sl. nos. 1, 2, 6 and 7, 5, 10 respectively. When the dimethylformamide was replaced with methanol, the change was pale yellow to red for compounds sl. nos. 2-4,

6-9, and yellow to dark for compounds sl. nos. 1, 5 and 10.

These compounds were also titrated potentiometrically using platinum electrodes. The platinum electrode was found most satisfactory for the titration of hydroxamic acids in non-aqueous media. The results are shown in Table 2. The thermodynamic ionisation constants are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—NON-AQUEOUS TITRATION DATA AND IONISATION CONSTANTS* OF HYDROXAMIC ACIDS

Sl. no.*	Mol. weight (Calcd.)	Mol. weight (Found)		p <i>K</i> _a
		Visible	Potentiometric	
1.	237.64	237.2	237.55	10.69
2.	253.70	253.9	253.68	10.25
3.	248.66	248.2	248.70	10.75
4.	298.72	298.9	298.68	10.30
5.	247.68	247.9	247.75	10.77
6.	237.64	237.8	237.70	10.69
7.	253.70	253.5	253.65	10.36
8.	248.66	248.6	248.59	10.58
9.	298.72	298.3	298.70	10.30
10.	247.68	247.3	247.58	10.51

*In 50% (v/v) dioxan-water media at 25°.

**Compounds same as in Table 1.

Alkaline hydrolysis : The rate constants (*K*) on the alkaline hydrolysis of the hydroxamic acids are given in Table 3 which is perhaps self-explanatory.

TABLE 3—ALKALINE HYDROLYSIS OF CHLORO-SUBSTITUTED-HYDROXAMIC ACIDS IN 50% (v/v) DIOXAN-WATER MEDIA AT 25°

Hydroxamic acid=0.01 *M* (in dioxane), NaOH=0.1 *M* (in 50% v/v dioxane), FeCl₃=1 ml (0.2% w/v in 1.0 *M* HCl), Temp.=25±0.1°, Order of reaction: 1st order

Sl. no.*	λ _{max} of complex		<i>K</i> × 10 ³ min
	nm	nm	
1.	540		1.1
2.	540		1.3
3.	525		13.5
4.	520		83.3
5.	530		8.7
6.	535		1.8
7.	535		2.2
8.	525		18.8
9.	520		95.5
10.	525		10.6

*Compounds same as in Table 1.

From the experimental results it is inferred that the rate constants are of pseudo-first order. The plots of $\log (A_0 - A_\infty / A_t - A_\infty)$ against the time t showed a linearity in case of all the hydroxamic acids studied, which further confirmed the first order reaction.

It is not confirmed whether the water molecule is attacking the hydroxamic acid molecule or the hydroxamate anion, and the possible rate reaction mechanism is as follows.

Substitutions R_1 and R in the hydroxamate moiety have marked effect on the rate of alkaline hydrolysis of the hydroxamic acids, which is evident from the Table 2.

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